

PROGRAMS

PROGnostics based Reliability Analysis for Maintenance Scheduling
Project number 767287

D9.4

Data Management Plan - preliminary

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Executive summary

The PROGRAMS project participates in H2020 pilot action on open access to research data. This deliverable, the PROGRAMS Data Management Plan, describes the research data that will be collected and generated during the project and explains which part of it will be shared for public re-use.

PROGRAMS is an industry-driven innovation action that will deliver solutions to improve the maintenance scheduling for production facilities. As most of the project outcomes are susceptible of being protected for exploitation, this preliminary Data Management Plan try to identify as clearly as possible which data will be kept confidential and which will be made openly available. The PROGRAMS management plan will be updated as the project progresses. A final version of the Data Management Plan will be available at the end of the project in D9.5.

1 Data Summary

The PROGRAMS project will produce new data by collecting information from the sensors and the controllers installed on its two pilot lines (WP7) and on machines made available for laboratory demos (WP6). The data will be used to train, test and validate the PROGRAMS solutions for maintenance scheduling and prediction of equipment components remaining useful life. As a general principle, the owner of the production equipment from which the data is collected will own the data themselves (e.g. sensors records, reports, etc.) but access rights to these data will be granted for the project duration to the consortium for project internal use. A part of these data will be made public on the conditions detailed in the remainder of the document (open data). The PROGRAMS consortium believes that data that will be created, collected and shared during the project will allow European researchers to build on PROGRAMS research results, speeding up innovation and avoiding the duplication of the effort of such data collection. All data not open to public will be defined hereinafter private data.

The following categories of data are considered for collection (and possible public sharing) purposes:

- Sensors and controllers data from production equipment: raw data will be recorded and stored both on the servers of the data owners and on the PROGRAMS cloud databases and will size in the range of terabytes. Additional datasets, including existing material collected by partners in the Consortium before the beginning of the project, will be made available for statistical analysis.
- Formulas, libraries and software: several PROGRAMS solutions will be software tools that will deal with different objectives (including but not limited to lifecycle analysis, usage computation, remaining useful life assessment and maintenance scheduling).

2 FAIR data

The current version of the PROGRAMS Data Management Plan is based on the EC DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN guidelines and the H2020 template “Data management plan v1.0” released on 2016-10-13. These guidelines have explicit recommendations for full life cycle management through the implementation of the FAIR principles, which states that the data produced shall be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). The implementation of the FAIR principles is intended as a conceptual integration rather than a technical integration.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?	The data will be characterized by metadata as additional result of the data pre-processing algorithms (T2.3) automatically after its collection. Handle/DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) could be assigned for persistent identification and citability of the various open dataset.
What naming conventions do you follow?	Naming conventions will be defined as part of T5.2 activity, following the guidelines of the ISO/IEC 11179 – Part 5 standard. The PROGRAMS dataset identification should follow the naming: Data_<owner>_<data source>_<timestamp of dataset>_<dataset title>. Example: Data_FIDIA_DL155_2018-05-01#11:15_SensorData.
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	Search keywords will be included to metadata to increase open data re-usability.
Do you provide clear version numbers?	The standard GNU version numbering scheme will be used for all the PROGRAMS software tools.

<p>What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</p>	<p>Sensor data collected will be characterized by relevant metadata as additional result of the data pre-processing algorithms (T2.3) automatically after its collection. Metadata will follow the guidelines of the ISO/IEC 11179 standard. Typical metadata will include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facility Name • Machine name • Timestamp • Units • Sensor system source • ...
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2.2 Making data openly accessible

<p>Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if relevant provisions are made in the consortium agreement and are in line with the reasons for opting out.</p>	<p>Sensor data collected will be characterized by relevant metadata and moved on public repositories (thus becoming open data) whenever they do not hinder the commercial activities of the owners and under the explicit consensus of the data owner themselves. In line of principle, data generated while processing test parts for the PROGRAMS project will be considered open, while data collected during the commercial activities of the end users will be considered private.</p> <p>The IPR property of the software data (source codes, algorithms, formulas) is attributed following the lines of the Consortium Agreement. In line of principle, the public sharing of such information is currently deemed incompatible with the obligation to protect results that can reasonably be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited, thus these data will be shared only as meta-code and only after the Consortium has agreed on the disclosure.</p>
<p>How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?</p>	<p>Sensor and software data will be recorded and stored both on the servers of the data owners and on the PROGRAMS cloud databases and will size in the range of terabytes. Open data will be copied on public repositories.</p>
<p>What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?</p>	<p>The private data will be accessible to the consortium through web services developed in T5.2. Public data access methods will be responsibility of the selected public repositories provider.</p>
<p>Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?</p>	<p>The private data will be accessible to the consortium by web services developed in T5.2. Deliverable D5.2 will detail the methods by which the data can be accessed. Public data access methods documentation will be responsibility of the selected public repositories provider.</p>
<p>Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?</p>	<p>As will all PROGRAMS source code, due to IPR issues only algorithms in metalanguage are foreseen for open sharing.</p>
<p>Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.</p>	<p>The PROGRAMS cloud for private data have not been selected yet (Amazon, IBM, Azure and 1and1 are currently considered). Figshare, Zenodo and OpenAire are currently taken into consideration as open data repositories.</p>
<p>Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?</p>	<p>The PROGRAMS cloud databases for private data has not been selected yet.</p>
<p>If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?</p>	<p>Access to electronic files and systems will be restricted using privilege levels and passwords.</p>
<p>Is there a need for a data access committee?</p>	<p>All private data will be accessible by the whole consortium and all public data will be free to use, thus no data access committee is needed.</p>
<p>Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine readable license)?</p>	<p>All private data will be accessible by the whole consortium, thus no further access description is needed.</p>

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Access to electronic files and systems will be restricted using privilege levels and passwords. These systems will allow to univocally ascertain the identity of the person accessing the data.
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2.3 Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?	Data archived on public infrastructures must be usable beyond the original purpose or the consortium it was collected by. Open data formats shall meet accepted international standards and documentation will be provided by drawing information from selected sections of project deliverables.
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	Standards such as the ISO/IEC 11179 Metadata Registry (MDR), which addresses issues in the metadata and data modelling space, will be taken into account.
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow interdisciplinary interoperability?	The existence of standard vocabularies for PROGRAMS data will be checked. If none will be deemed suitable, data types will be registered following internal codifications specified in deliverable D9.6.
In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?	See above.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	The data available for re-use (open data) will be findable and reusable through the final depositing repository (Figshare, Zenodo or OpenAire), the latest by the end of the project.
When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.	In general, open data shall be made publicly available as soon as possible and without undue delay. All undisclosed open data will be moved on public repositories at the end of the project and will remain re-usable after the end of the project by anyone interested in it, with no access or time restrictions.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.	The private data will be confidential and only the members of the consortium will have access to it. Specific portions of it will become open and will include descriptions of the datasets. These data will be anonymized so as not to have any potential correlation and identification.
How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	All private data has been identified as to be destroyed from the PROGRAMS cloud servers at the end of the project. All private data to be preserved or that can be preserved by owners beyond the end of the project will be kept in owners' servers only, and maintenance will be carried out by owners. Partners can continue exploiting private data by direct agreement with the data owners. All open data moved on public repositories at the end of the project will remain re-usable after the end of the project with no access or time restrictions.
Are data quality assurance processes described?	The quality of the dataset is guaranteed by the pre-processing algorithms (T2.3).

3 Allocation of resources

The cost for making the data FAIR (including its coverage) is detailed in the following table:

Activity	Private data	Open data
Data description	The data will be characterized by metadata as additional result of the data pre-processing algorithms (T2.3) automatically after its collection, effectively removing this cost.	
Data cleaning	The creation of specific data lakes is the objective of T5.1 and will thus be performed at no additional cost.	
Documentation	The data documentation (methodologies for collecting, creating, processing and quality controlled) will be available for the consortium in the project deliverables.	Documentation of open data will be published on the PROJECT website at no extra cost. Information will be drawn from selected sections of internal deliverables.
Formatting and organising	Data files will be formatted in clear structures defined in D6.1 at no extra cost, since the consortium agrees on the need of an efficient data management.	
Digitisation	All the data generated during the process will be stored in digital form. Non digital maintenance data created before the project and made available by partners will be digitalized as part of the activity of T4.1 at no extra cost.	
File format	All the data generated during the process will be stored in standard formats defined in D6.1. Thus this activity will require no extra cost.	
Data storage	The cost for storing data on the PROGRAMS cloud database has a wide range of prices that depends on the cloud service provider. This cost will be known only when the data storage needs will be properly characterized.	Figshare, Zenodo and OpenAire are currently taken into consideration as open data repositories. Deposit and access are free.
Data transfer	The cost for transferring data to/from the PROGRAMS components to the PROGRAMS cloud database has a wide range of prices that depends on the cloud service provider. This cost will be known only when the data access needs will be properly characterized.	Additional cost could be needed to transfer the open data from the project databases to the public repository. The cost will be known only once the project and public databases will be selected.
Anonymization	Not needed	The data will be cleared by any company reference before public sharing as a part of the Data transfer process (see above).
Data security	The security on the data on the cloud server is usually included in the Data storage and transfer cost.	The open data will be public available, thus the only security issue (that will be responsibility of the data repositories) is against accidental or voluntary data destruction.

FIDIA, as coordinator, is responsible for implementing the data management plan (DMP).

All private data to be preserved by owners beyond the end of the project will be kept in owners' servers only, and relevant cost will be covered by owners.

4 Data security

The consortium agrees that that all reasonable steps should be taken to ensure that collected data is secure, and the following steps will be considered for implementation:

- Access to electronic files and systems should be restricted using privilege levels and passwords.
- Regular password changes should be enforced and the number of attempted logins limited.
- Equipment access should be restricted to authorised personnel.
- Computers and other devices should be locked when unattended and should be logged-off at the end of a session.
- Redundant data (such as cloud stored data after the end of the project) should be wiped, overwritten or shredded to avoid data recovery.
- Appropriate back-up and storage should be observed.
- Portable storage media should be stored carefully.

- Data must be kept as secure as possible, using encryption, de-personalisation and password-protection if possible. Recognised firewalls should be installed.
- Hard copy papers containing relevant project information (maintenance records, equipment performances, cost management documents) should be shredded before disposal and should not be used as scrap paper.
- Files should be stored on partners' servers only if the repositories are adequately certified. When cloud servers are selected, a careful analysis of the provider security standard should be performed.

5 Ethical aspects

PROGRAMS does not handle personal data thus there are no ethical issues associated to the project data.

Conclusions

The preliminary work of T9.2 on the data management in the PROGRAMS project complies with the FAIR-principles, in the sense that all aspects of the FAIR principles are being considered. The next version of the Data Management Plan (D9.5) shall explain how the FAIR principles have been specifically implemented.